

ELECTROCHEMICAL INDUSTRIES: POSSIBILITIES IN INDIA *

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The application of the electric current to chemical industry, apart from its use as a source of power, has become at the present time of such immense significance to modern life that its importance in the development of the great basic industries of this country would be manifest from a consideration specially of India's existing and potential mineral and power resources. It is indeed a far cry from the simple experiments with the voltaic pile conducted by Sir Humphrey Davy in the early years of the 19th century on the decomposition of caustic soda, to the present day prodigious plants of the Alcoa in Tennessee Valley and other places of the U.S.A. using up nearly a third of a million horse power, or the copper plants of the Chile Copper Company in Chuquicamata, Chile, or the high frequency induction furnaces of the Ajax-Northrup type used in alloy melting, where the only practicable limits to the temperatures reached are those imposed by the capacity of the materials of construction to withstand the temperatures created. Electrochemical industries cover to-day almost every field of national endeavour. The following list¹ of some of the more important materials turned out by the electrolytic cell and the electric furnace shows the astonishing range of their usefulness both in times of peace and in war. The finished products together with raw materials used in their manufacture and their applications, classified according to their mode of production, are given in Tables I-IV.

TABLE I

Products of the electrolytic cell

(a) Electroseparation.			(b) Electrolytic oxidation.		
Product.	Raw material.	Applications.	Product.	Raw material.	Applications.
Chlorine	Salt, water	Bleaching, gas warfare, hydrochloric acid, chemical syntheses, sanitation.	Potassium chlorate	Potassium chloride	Matches and dyeing.
Hydrogen	Caustic soda and water.	Balooning, hydrogenated fats.	Potassium persulphate	Potassium sulphate	Oxidising agent, bleaching.
Oxygen	" "	Oxywelding, oxycutting.	Perborates	Borax	Bleaching agent for textiles.
Caustic soda	Salt, water	Soap, paper, dyestuffs, drugs, explosives.	Sodium bichromate	Chromium salts	Dyeing and tanning.
			White lead	Lead	Paint pigment.
(c) Electrowinning and refining.			(c) Electrowinning and refining.		
Product.	Raw material.	Applications.	Product.	Raw material.	Applications.
Copper	Copper ore, crude copper	Electrical and brass industries.	Cadmium	Zinc electro-winning slimes	Plating, alloys.
Zinc	Zinc ore	Brass industry, galvanising.	Chromium (electro plating)	Chromic and sulphuric acids.	Plating.
Manganese	Manganese ore	Ferrous and non-ferrous alloys.	Nickel	Crude nickel	Alloys, plating industry, dairy equipment, utensils.
Tin	Impure tin, Tin dross.	Tinplate industry.	Lead	Crude lead	Alloys, fittings, acid chambers.
Gold	Anode slime from copper	Coinage, jewellery, industrial alloys.			
Silver	Do	Do			
Platinum	Nickel slimes	Catalysts, jewellery, alloys.			

* Presidential address at the 21st Annual General meeting of the Indian Chemical Society, held on Jan. 3, 1945 at Nagpur.

TABLE II

Products from fused electrolytes

Product.	Raw material.	Applications.	Product.	Raw material.	Applications.
Aluminium	Bauxite	Electric power transmission cables, light weight alloys for aeroplanes, automobiles, aluminothermic reactions, ammonal, acid containers, cooking utensils.	Sodium	Caustic soda or salt.	Peroxides, cyanides, bleaching, mining, alloys tetraethyl lead, organic synthesis.
Magnesium	Magnesium chloride or Magnesium oxide.	Light weight alloys, tracer bullets, flashlight powders and flares.	Barium	Barium chloride	Alloys, electron emission.
			Beryllium	Beryl	Light alloys.
			Cerium metal	Rare earth chlorides	Pyrophoric alloys, tracer bullets and shells.
			Thorium	Potassium thorium fluoride	Electron emission, X-Ray targets.

TABLE III

Products of the electric furnace

Product.	Raw material.	Applications.	Product.	Raw material.	Applications.
Alumina (fused)	Bauxite	Abrasives and refractories.	Ferro-vanadium	Iron vanadate	Special and automobile steel.
Quartz (fused)	Quartz rock	Optical uses, heat resisting materials.	Calcium carbide	Lime and coke	Acetylene for welding, cutting, lighting, for chemical synthesis leading to plastics, synthetic rubber.
Graphite	Anthracite coal	Electrodes, lubricants.	Calcium cyanamide	Calcium carbide and nitrogen of air	Fertiliser, ammonia, cyanides.
Ferrochrome	Chrome ore	Special and high speed steels, armour plate, projectiles.	Carbon bi-sulphide	Coke and sulphur	Solvent, insecticide, carbon tetrachloride, artificial silk (viscose).
Ferro-manganese	Manganese ore and coke	Steels, permanganates.	Nitric acid	Air	Explosives, fertilisers.
Ferro-silicon	Iron, silica and coke	Steels, acid resistant iron.			
Ferro-tungsten	Tungsten ore	Special and high speed steels.			

TABLE IV

Organic products

Product.	Raw material.	Applications.	Product.	Raw material.	Applications.
Anthra-quinone	Anthracene	Dyestuffs.	Benzidine	Nitrobenzene	Dyestuffs.
<i>para</i> -Amino phenol	Nitrobenzene	Dyestuffs, drugs and developers.	Sorbitol	Glucose solution	Resin, plasticisers, Vitamin C synthesis
			Mannitol	Do	Esters, ethers, chemicals.

Electricity thus enters into the production of a large variety of basic materials—metals, alloys and chemicals, fertilisers, abrasives, graphite electrodes, primary and secondary batteries, etc., many of which serve again as raw materials for other industries. In some of these the use of electricity is indispensable as in the production of aluminium, sodium, magnesium, calcium carbide, fused alumina, graphite, etc., while in others, it leads to a purer product and is more economical as in the production of copper, tin, lead, nickel, gold and ferro alloys and special steels.

During the past decade the production of metals and alloys has taken a steep upward turn chiefly because of improvements in the methods of manufacture, lowering in the costs of production, discoveries of new uses and development of backward areas. Table V gives figures for the world production of some of the important metals during the year 1937.

TABLE V²

Copper	2,434,000 short tons.	Aluminium	490,600 short tons.
Lead	1,893,200	Ferro alloys ³	2,180,000 metric tons
Zinc	1,845,000	Magnesium ⁴	25,000
Tin	205,200	Sodium (1940) ⁵	50,000

In recent years an additional impetus has been provided by the War, the Aluminium Company of America (Alcoa) alone having produced in 1939, 146,000 tons⁶ and embarked on an expansion programme involving an expenditure of 30,000,000 dollars, increasing the production to 178,600 tons in 1942. Similarly the Dow Chemical Company in U.S.A. with the support of the Government, has launched on the production of magnesium aiming at the target figure of 362,500 tons by the end of 1943 at a cost of 339,000,000 dollars.⁷ In Germany the production of aluminium for the year 1937 was 127,500 tons accounting for a fourth of the total world output of this metal that year.⁸ These figures convey an idea of the enormous scales on which some of the major electrochemical industries are being operated at the present day.

An abundant supply of cheap electrical power which is the raw material *par excellence* for this industry must be considered to be the most important single factor in the development of electrochemical industries in any country. A study of the current requirements for various electrochemical industries is, therefore, of great interest from this point of view. The following table in which the cost of electricity in relation to selling price of electrochemical and electrometallurgical products is given reveals the enormous quantities and the wide variations of the power utilized.

TABLE VI⁸

Product.	Kw. per ton.	Cost of current per ton.		Current cost as % of selling price.	Product.	Kw. per ton.	Cost of current per ton.		Current cost as % of selling price.
		£	£				£	£	
Ferromanganese	3500	2'3	19	12	Cadmium	1,250	1'5	270	0'6
Ferrosilicon	4500	3'0	11	27	Nickel	2,500	1'7	180	0'9
Ferrotungsten	8600	5'75	524	1'1	Lead (Refining)	100	0'07	15	0'5
Ferrochrome	7000	4'70	23	20	Calcium carbide	3,000	2'0	11	18
Aluminium	18,000	12'0	94	13	Chlorine	3,000	2'0	19	11
Magnesium,					Caustic soda	3,000	2'0	18	11
Electrolytic	20,000	13'4	168	8'0	Silicon carbide	8,500	5'7	39	15
Electrothermal	24,000	16'0	168	9'5	Aluminium abrasives	2,500	1'6	—	—
Sodium	15,000	10'0	—	—	Hydrogen	67,000	45'0	—	—
Beryllium	65,000	43'4	—	—	Sodium chlorate	6,700	4'5	30	15
Cerium	25,000	16'7	—	—	Potassium chlorate	5,800	3'9	36	11
Copper (extraction)	2,500	1'6	42	4'0	Graphite	3,900	2'6	—	—
Zinc	3,500	2'4	14	17					

It is obvious, therefore, that for the successful operation of any electrochemical industry, the cost of power should be as low as possible, and the controversy,⁹ sometimes rather acrimonious, which is being carried on at the present moment regarding the relative merits

and economics of power generation by hydroelectric and thermal plants should be of special interest with reference to this country. According to one view¹⁰ hydroelectric power can never be surpassed or replaced as the cheapest source of power for the following reasons :—

(1) In a hydroelectric station, the capital cost is made up by 20 per cent plant and the rest for dams, aqueducts, etc. The latter have an almost indefinite life. Hence in spite of increased capital cost the amortization rate is low. The reverse is the case with thermal stations in which over 75 per cent is plant and the rest buildings.

(2) The maintenance and running costs are low. In a thermal plant in addition to increased cost under the above heads must be added the heavy cost of fuel.

(3) At a hydroelectric station the maximum cost is known from the beginning while with steam, the price may vary with the price of coal or other fuel.

(4) The cost of electricity generated at a hydroelectric station with a capital cost of £. 49 per installed kilowatt is likely to be the same as at a thermal station with a capital cost of £. 18 per installed kilowatt because of lower amortization rates in the former case and increased maintenance and running expenses of the latter. (These figures apply more to Britain where the most favourable sites have been exploited already. Donkin gives the capital cost of hydroelectric stations as £. 35 per installed kilowatt in Great Britain, £ 36 in Canada, and an average roughly from £ 18 to £ 50 per installed kilowatt in U.S.A.)

According to a comparative study made in 1936-38 in Scotland on the cost of power generated from water and of that from a steam plant situated in the neighbourhood of a coal field, with coal at 15 shillings per ton the cost of current by steam was double.¹⁰ Another careful estimate of the comparative costs in the two cases has led to the conclusion that, excluding charges on capital, the cost in the case of water power plant was 0.015 d. per unit while that in the thermal plant was 0.96 d. per unit.

On the other hand, there is the other view⁹ which is equally insistent about the thermal station having many decided advantages over the hydroelectric power station, the following being the main arguments advanced in favour of the thermal stations :

(1) Because of lower capital cost, the undertaking would be much less vulnerable to fluctuation on the demand for power.

(2) It would not be subject to compulsory stoppages due to drought or ice conditions.

(3) In many cases waste-heat is also required as in the production of aluminium from alumina and the thermal cost of energy may be reduced by half by proper co-ordination. The fuel consumption of modern boilers is extremely low, the best present day practice corresponding to 0.96 lb. of coal per kw. hr. The power output at existing thermal stations can be augmented to any desired extent by the installation of superposed high pressure boilers.

(4) In general the cost of transmitting electricity by power lines (Morrow, *loc. cit.*) is about 2½ times the cost of transporting fuels to distances of 50-100 miles. The advantage would, therefore, lie with the thermal generator situated at the load.

(5) The most favourable sites for water power development have already been tapped and future installations will be costlier.

We may now consider how far these arguments for or against hydroelectric or thermal plant affect our case. India's coal resources are known to be concentrated only in

certain in small areas, and the deposits which are not unlimited, are being used up at an alarming rate. With the exception of Germany where the immense deposits of lignite have perhaps been mainly responsible for retarding water-power development, electrochemical industries have made the greatest headway in countries with extensive water power resources such as the U.S.A., Canada, the Scandinavian countries, Italy, France and Switzerland. It can hardly be disputed, therefore, that unless fresh deposits of coal are discovered in India at several sites situated favourably with respect to raw materials, our industries must depend to a large extent on hydroelectric power.¹² In Table VII the potential water power resources of different countries and the extent to which development has progressed are given.¹⁰

TABLE VII

Country.	H. P. potential.	Developed H. P.	Country.	H. P. potential.	Developed H. P.
Great Britain and Ireland	1,257,000	488,000	Germany	8,800,000	3,500,000 (1930)
Canada	34,000,000	8,845,000 (1942)	Switzerland	4,000,000	3,500,000 (1933)
Newfoundland	400,000	—	France	10,000,000	4,220,000 (1935)
South Africa	1,600,000	—	Italy	9,000,000	7,000,000 (1933)
India	27,000,000	500,000 (approx.)	Russia	270,000,000	30,000,000 (1937)
Norway	12,000,000	2,737,000 (1932)	U. S. A.	80,000,000	21,000,000 (1940)
		(since then great progress has been made.)		(only 50% can be developed.)	(in 1943, an additional 5,000,000 H. P. would have been available from the new Federal Projects)
Sweden	10,000,000	2,000,000 (1933)			

A glance at the table reveals the very backward position which India occupies in the matter of power development. It would be seen that as far as India is concerned, hardly 2% of her potential resources has been developed yet and there is nothing to prevent large schemes of expansion of water power being contemplated, undeterred by the arguments advanced against it in other countries. In areas deficient in such resources but with an abundance of cheap coal, as in Bihar or Bengal, thermal installations will necessarily get the preference.

In order to make the best use¹⁰ of the water power resources of any country, it is necessary to have a comprehensive inland water survey involving (1) a systematic gauging of all important rivers, (2) rainfall and snow records and (3) a study of absorption, evaporation and ground storage. Such essential work must obviously be undertaken under state auspices in order that the information may have continuity and be available to all. In U. S. A. all such basic information is collected by the Weather Bureau and the Geological Survey which are departments of the Government. Till 1932, the development was left only to private initiative and enterprise, but since then the Federal Power Commission has launched vast schemes like the Boulder Dam and Grand Coulee Dam projects, which are designed not only for power supply but also for water supply and river regulation. Similarly, Canada, Switzerland, Italy and the Scandinavian countries have Government departments responsible for inland water supply. It is clear that a co-ordinating agency for obtaining and distributing correct basic information on all such matters must be established in this country before any systematic development of power on a large scale can be contemplated. From this point of view the development of electricity cannot possibly be relegated as a provincial subject. Unless the controlling interest

vests in the Central Government which alone can sponsor large schemes of power development, there can be no prospect of a flourishing national electrochemical industry operating in India on a competitive basis with those of other countries.

It is needless to state that India has still to find a place on the map of electrochemical industries of the world. Plants for the production of caustic soda and chlorine are now being operated by the I.C.I. at Rishra, the Tatas at Mithapur and by the Mettur Chemicals.¹² In addition there may be several smaller installations for the manufacture of caustic soda and chlorine as at the paper mills at Dalmianagar of the Rohtas Industries, with a limited production for specific demands. Aluminium metal from Indian bauxite is also being manufactured in recent years through the joint enterprise of the British Aluminium Company, the Aluminium Company of Canada and others, but the exact figures of production and current consumption are not available. Apart from these India does not appear to have any other large electrochemical industries.

The import figures taken from the Annual Statement of the Sea Borne Trade of British India for the year 1937-1939 issued by the D. G. Commercial Intelligence and Statistics for some of the important materials which are mainly or exclusively produced by electrochemical methods are given in Table VIII.

TABLE VIII

Product.	Weight.	Value.	Product.	Weight.	Value.
Aluminium unwrought, sheets and other manufactures	66,832 cwts.	Rs. 52,70,222	Zinc	446,657 cwt.	Rs. 76,78,474
Ferro alloys	3,092 tons.	7,49,006	Caustic soda	578,485 "	42,80,555
Copper, unwrought, wrought and wire excluding telegraph wire	326,063 cwts.	1,39,79,489	Bleaching powder	237,303 "	13,12,915
Lead	156,018 "	28,87,032	Chlorine (liquid)	668,428 lbs.	2,49,220
Tin	60,415 "	85,47,596	Calcium carbide	54,445 cwts.	5,94,122
			Potassium chlorate	42,207 "	7,07,912
			Sodium bichromate	20,762 "	4,65,925
					Total Rs. 4,67,22,468

It will be interesting to examine how far our position in regard to the raw materials required for these electrochemical industries warrants the import in large quantities of the products of these industries into India.

Aluminium.—Bauxite has so far been the only source for the production of this metal. To quote the Records of the Geological Survey of India (Volume 70, page 352, 1936) "The Indian bauxite industry has never been actively developed in spite of several efforts, justified by the large occurrences of this material in various parts of the peninsula. The trade so far has depended on small orders from oil companies for the purification of kerosene, and smaller demands by chemical companies for the preparation of aluminous sulphates, etc." Discussing the industrial possibilities of Indian Bauxite, Chatterjee, Roy and Das-Gupta¹³ state that the available deposits are low in silica, high in titanium oxide, of moderate iron content and lend themselves readily to treatment by the Bayer process and 95 per cent of the alumina are recoverable. As far as our present knowledge goes, India is deficient in copper, tin and zinc but bauxite of good quality is available in enormous quantities at several places and the use of aluminium and aluminium based alloys in place of copper and its alloys should be extremely desirable in the interests of this country.

Magnesium.—The raw materials for magnesium production are usually magnesite or dolomite which are converted into the chloride before electrolysis, or magnesium chloride itself where it is available. Extensive deposits of magnesite of very high purity are known to occur in the Salem District (Madras). This material should lend itself very well to treatment by the "Oxide process" which after receding into the background for some years appears to have gained in importance during the last few years. The Austro-American Magnesite Company at Radentheim have been operating this process¹⁴, with a power consumption of 23 kw. hr. per kg. of metal ingot (including 4 kw. hrs. for keeping hydrogen in the flue) as against the 25 kw. hr. required for the chloride process. For the processing of the cheap magnesium chloride of the Tatas at Mithapur a modified Dow process may prove suitable.

Manganese.—Manganese ore of high quality is available in large amounts in India. The export of manganese ore in the year 1937-1938 amounted to 1,001,096 tons with a value of Rs. 2,21,28,945. In this connexion, the development recently of an electrolytic method for the extraction of manganese¹⁵ should be of particular interest in this country.

Chromium.—Chromite ore of good quality is available chiefly in Baluchistan, Mysore and in Bihar. The export of chromite ore in 1937-1938 was 41,452 tons with a value of Rs. 12,69,078. The production of ferrochrome and sodium bichromate is a distinct possibility.

Caustic Soda, Chlorine and Bleaching Powder.—Extensive deposits of salt are available in several parts of the country and some of them are favourably placed with regard to power. Expansion in the production of caustic soda can be achieved without difficulty but the disposal of chlorine may remain a problem for some time till increased activity in other fields of chemical industry and in sanitation leads to greater use.

Calcium Carbide.—The raw materials for the production of calcium carbide are limestone and coke. Limestone of high quality is available in almost every province and the substitution of charcoal, if available at cheap prices, for coke has been found to lead to smoother furnace operation and to a purer product. The production of calcium carbide in this country will depend mainly on the location of the factory in places favourably disposed in regard to power.

Organic Compounds.—Although in bulk and value, organic products cannot compare with the inorganic products cited above, they find such important uses as dye intermediates, photographic developers and drugs that it is very regrettable that so little prominence has been given to the manufacture of organic compounds by electrolytic methods. This is not because electrolytic methods have not been employed in organic industries—in fact numerous applications have occurred—but to quote Thatcher¹⁶, one of the pioneers of technical electrochemistry in America, "It will probably be difficult if not impossible to cite another branch of applied science in which such extreme reticence has been maintained". The typical reactions of organic chemistry like reduction, oxidation and substitution may often be carried out with ease if not elegance by electrolytic methods. Expensive reducing or oxidising agents like zinc, tin, lead peroxide, or chromic oxide are dispensed with and there are no sludges of inorganic bye-products to remove. Once the right conditions for a particular desired result have been determined the electrolytic method has proved superior to the chemical method because of the greater ease of control over the reaction.

It would appear from the report of the raw material position for the dyestuffs industry in India by Pai and Venkataraman¹⁷, in which a promising survey has been made of the availability of the primary materials like benzene, toluene, naphthalene, etc., that the application of electrochemical methods to the production of technically important organic compounds is another promising field lying unexplored. Researches on the manufacture of dye-intermediates like benzidine, tolidine and dianisidine and of *para*-aminophenol which have been in progress for the past three years in the Chemistry laboratories of the Presidency College, Madras, under the auspices of the Board of Scientific and Industrial Research have proved beyond doubt that both benzidine and aminophenol, the production of which have been carried out on a pilot plant scale, can be manufactured satisfactorily by the electrochemical method which is superior in ease of operation, purity of product and cost of production to the chemical method.

The raw material resources in respect of several electrochemical industries are satisfactory. The deficiencies of copper, zinc and tin are serious, but by increased use of aluminium, as is being done at present in other countries deficient in copper, this can be overcome. While the Geological Survey of India has done very valuable work, its activities, as has been pointed out by many eminent scientists and industrialists, have been on a scale wholly inadequate for achieving great results for a subcontinent like India.

As regards power, while it is insufficient at the present time for operating electrochemical industries on a large scale, the proposed priority for the development of power in post-war reconstruction should make sufficient power available in the near future, for the creation of a number of first rate electrochemical industries. Similarly the deficiency of the very limited technical knowledge and skill in the country for operating electrochemical plants should be largely remedied by the proposal of the Government to establish a central Electrochemical Research Institute, and to depute a large number of science graduates abroad for training in industrial research. The extent to which the major electrochemical industries have developed in advanced countries has been the result of the closest collaboration between the Engineer, the Metallurgist and the Chemist and any planning for the establishment of electrochemical industries will necessarily have to be done in close co-ordination with planning for other industries in India. Thus, while the development of power is essential for electrochemical industries, it will also benefit agriculture by development of irrigation, not to mention numerous other industries using power and also the house-hold consumer. Similarly, if a reliable survey is made of the mineral wealth of this country, the major beneficiaries will be other industries, chemical and otherwise, besides the electrochemical industries.

From the considerations set forth in the preceding paragraphs, it appears that the following steps are urgently called for as essential preliminaries to the establishment of electrochemical industries in this country :

(1) A re-examination of the water power resources of India by a Central Water Power Commission with experts from America and Europe in the staff and aided by departments like the Geological Survey of India and the Meteorological department. The report that Mr. W. L. Voorguin, Chief of the Project Planning Division, T. V. A. would shortly arrive in India to advise the newly constituted Central Technical Power Board is most welcome from this point of view.

(2) A survey of the mineral wealth of this country on a much more extensive and intensified scale should be undertaken. The example of the U. S. S. R. provides an excellent model to work upon.

(3) Wherever the position relating to availability of raw material and power is favourable, as in the case of the manufacture of aluminium, magnesium, caustic soda, calcium carbide, etc., the manufacture of these materials should be undertaken under state auspices.

(4) The establishment of one or more electrochemical research institutes headed by experts to solve problems of the electrochemical industry as they arise and to do exploratory work for the exploitation of local raw materials.

(5) The immediate training of a large number of Indians in electrochemical industries in America and Europe by agreement with the industries concerned, on suitable terms.

(6) A comprehensive survey on the availability of raw material for electrochemical and electrometallurgical industries in places where there are projects for power development.

Whether India by her own efforts unaided by other advanced countries, can attain a place of emineuce in this industry worthy of her raw material resources, her potential reserves of power and her great population seems at present to be doubtful. It should not, however, be difficult to devise a scheme of co-operation of the Indian industry with other well-established foreign firms, both in the matter of capital and technical skill and knowledge on suitable and equitable terms. It is hoped that those in charge of planning will launch on carefully drawn and co-ordinated projects, with boldness and imagination for the results to be achieved are no less than the happiness and prosperity of the people of this country.

B I B L I O G R A P H Y

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